

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Assessing the maturity of integrated care systems as a means to accelerate adoption and lessons in using the SCIROCCO tool across Europe

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Background: Healthy ageing and high quality care are a global challenge. Multiple chronic conditions and the complexity of needs arising from them demands a rethinking of delivery systems, innovation, and resourcing. The need for sustainable resourcing drives professionals, end-users and the wider public and private sectors to draw on their experience and expertise to meet those needs. Tools and methodologies that help understand these complex transformational processes and orchestrate discussions of all stakeholders involved are core to this process.

A collaboration of over 30 European regions is engaged in the development of an online self-assessment tool enabled by the EU funded project - SCIROCCO. The online tool has been developed to help regions to assess their progress and maturity in the provision of innovative integrated care services and encourages knowledge transfer and scaling-up of innovative integrated care solutions to support the at-scale adoption of integrated care across Europe.

Aims and objectives: This workshop is an opportunity to explore the potential of the SCIROCCO self-assessment tool to facilitate collaboration and knowledge transfer that supports and accelerates the adoption of integrated care in Europe. The session will feature the experiences of three European regions - Basque Country Region in Spain, Norrbotten Region in Sweden and Puglia Region in Italy - of using the SCIROCCO tool. Each Region tested the tool in the process of assessing the maturity of their healthcare systems for the adoption of integrated care. The resulting assessments are now informing knowledge transfer activities in the form of twinning and coaching with the aim of facilitating improvement in the aspects of integrated care that the regions assessed themselves as being weaker.

Target audience: A wide spectrum of stakeholders is being targeted: national and regional decision-makers, service delivery organisations, healthcare professionals, industry and academia.

Henderson; Assessing the maturity of integrated care systems as a means to accelerate adoption and lessons in using the SCIROCCO tool across Europe

Learnings / Take away: The experience of over 30 regions and organisations testing the SCIROCCO tool demonstrate the clear benefits and added value of the self-assessment tool in stimulating multi-stakeholder discussions and learning on future directions in integrated care and transformation of health and care delivery systems.

Keywords: maturity; knowledge-transfer; scaling-up; transformation; assessment-tool
